

DCC Research Data Management Survey 2014 'From Strategy to Action' – Responses on Storage and Resourcing Questions

Introduction

The responses were grouped into three categories, the first two of which represent our target group of service managers in the 69 institutions who receive at least 10% of their funding from research, according to HESA's 2011-12 data (1). We received responses from 87 individuals in 61 institutions. Since most of the questions asked for individuals' views rather than a consolidated institutional view we encouraged multiple responses. We received these from 26 institutions. They were de-duplicated for the analysis of storage and resourcing questions, as here we were asking people to report facts as far as they knew them, rather than give their personal expectations or perspectives.

The deduplicated responses represent all 24 Russell Group institutions, and most of those in the target group who are not Russell Group members. Overall there were responses from 37% of the 163 UK Higher Education Institutions listed by HESA. For the purposes of the survey we grouped these as follows: -

- A Russell Group Institutions** (n=24, 100% response rate)
- B Others with research income at least 10%** (n=24, 55% response)
- C Other institutions** (n=13, 14% response)

1. How does or will your institution allocate storage for research data? (respondents could choose any applicable option)

	Russell Group		Other 10%+		Other		Overall	
All active research staff have a quota	9	43%	9	39%	4	31%	22	39%
Principal Investigators have a quota	4	19%	4	17%	0	0%	8	14%
Postgrad research students have a quota	4	19%	4	17%	2	15%	10	18%
Active research projects have a quota	1	5%	4	17%	1	8%	6	11%
Some staff may pool their storage quotas	3	14%	2	9%	0	0%	5	9%
Storage may be purchased	5	24%	8	35%	4	31%	17	30%
Don't know	2	10%	3	13%	4	31%	9	16%
Other *	8	38%	9	39%	4	31%	21	37%
Total (non-blank responses)	21		23		13		57	

¹ Higher Education Statistics Agency (2013) Table 5 - Income from research grants and contracts, other income - other services rendered, other income - other and endowment and investment income by HE institution 2011/12. Available at: <http://www.hesa.ac.uk>

Responses to 'other'

*This is part of a RDM Implementation Programme, not finalised; It will be appropriate for some data to be deposited in discipline-specific repositories. Institutional allocation is in addition to these. Policy requires ICT department to monitor integrity of external repositories at Library's request; currently everyone has access to a basic 25GB cloud storage allowance and the need to develop a procurement/charging model so researchers/projects can obtain more has been identified; Quota with purchase option above; Funded projects can apply for quota; some cost recovery planned; Currently all research staff can apply for archive data store; more storage to be purchased during 2014 and policy developed; Large scale storage available without quota; Allocation driven by Data Management Plans; Mixed model; distributed responsibility of individual departments; Storage provided on request (where possible); Faculties and Research Institutes have a quota; Storage above the standard can be requested; Departments have a quota; varies by discipline; Undecided

**this has yet to be decided; Research teams in Schools manage their own data; Not yet agreed - a mixed model is being discussed whereby the institution stores some datasets and others are stored at UKDA and similar; still investigating current take up and demand; Storage provided on request; This is being considered by ICTD at the moment; So far there has been no discussion on quota; Research projects can apply for a quota; Various of above are under consideration; A consultancy report was undertaken but the suggestions need resourced; researchers will be allocated data storage flexibly according to their needs; Proposing storage provided to schools; This is yet to be determined

***No policy at institutional level, managed by academic departments, in review but likely to be all staff and res students, Limited network storage on-demand, At present we are working on a request by request basis

2. How much 'free at point of use' storage is currently included in any quota?

	Russell Group		Other 10%+		Other		Overall	
<500Gb	3	15%	4	17%	1	8%	8	14%
500Gb to 1Tb	3	15%	4	17%	0	0%	7	13%
More than 1Tb	5	25%	2	9%	0	0%	7	13%
Don't know	6	30%	5	22%	9	69%	20	36%
Not relevant	3	15%	8	35%	3	23%	14	25%
Total (non-blank responses)	20		23		13		56	

3. How much 'free at point of use' storage do you expect your institution will be providing per quota by May 2015?

	Russell Group		Other 10%+		Other		Overall	
< 500Gb	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
500Gb to 1Tb	3	15%	4	18%	1	8%	8	15%
More than 1Tb	6	30%	5	23%	0	0%	11	20%
Don't know	9	45%	9	41%	10	83%	28	52%
Not relevant	2	10%	4	18%	1	8%	7	13%
Total (non-blank responses)	20		22		12		54	

4. What has been funded for your institution, and from which sources? (respondents could choose any applicable option)

a) New appointments in Research Data Management

	Russell Group		Other 10%+		Other		Overall	
Internal	17	89%	12	92%	3	60%	32	86%
Research grants	4	21%	1	8%	0	0%	5	14%
Other external	6	32%	1	8%	1	20%	8	22%
Don't know	1	5%	2	15%	1	20%	4	11%
Total (non-blank responses)	19		13		5		37	

b) Training and development of researchers, PhD students and support staff

Internal	16	89%	16	100%	8	89%	40	93%
Research grants	3	17%	0	0%	1	11%	4	9%
Other external	5	28%	2	13%	1	11%	8	19%
Don't know	1	6%	0	0%	0	0%	1	2%
Total (non-blank responses)	18		16		9		43	

	Russell Group		Other 10%+		Other		Overall		
c) Infrastructure or external provision of storage, data management and digital preservation									
Internal	20	91%	16	89%	5	100%	41	91%	
Research grants	9	41%	5	28%	1	20%	15	33%	
Other external	5	23%	4	22%	1	20%	10	22%	
Don't know	2	9%	0	0%	0	0%	2	4%	
Total (non-blank responses)	22		18		5		45		

5. Which of the following does your institution plan to seek funding for, and from what sources?

a) New appointments in Research Data Management

Internal	20	91%	15	83%	5	100%	40	89%
Research grants	6	27%	0	0%	1	20%	7	16%
Other external	3	14%	3	17%	0	0%	6	13%
Don't know	2	9%	0	0%	1	20%	3	7%
Total (non-blank responses)	20		17		8		45	

b) Training and development of researchers, PhD students and support staff

Internal	18	100%	12	71%	4	67%	34	83%
Research grants	4	22%	5	29%	1	17%	10	24%
Other external	3	17%	4	24%	0	0%	7	17%
Don't know	0	0%	3	18%	1	17%	4	10%
Total (non-blank responses)	18		17		6		41	

	Russell Group		Other 10%+		Other	Overall			
c) Infrastructure or external provision of storage, data management and digital preservation									
Internal	19	95%	11	52%	5	50%	35	69%	
Research grants	15	75%	16	76%	3	30%	34	67%	
Other external	5	25%	14	67%	4	40%	23	45%	
Don't know	0	0%	3	14%	0	0%	3	6%	
Total (non-blank responses)	20		21		10		51		

6. What proportion of overall staffing (FTE) for RDM do you expect to be resourced by restructuring existing roles?

None	3	14%	5	22%	2	15%	10	17%	
Most	13	59%	12	52%	3	23%	28	48%	
All	1	5%	1	4%	3	23%	5	9%	
Don't know	5	23%	5	22%	5	38%	15	26%	
Total (non-blank responses)	22		23		13		58		

7. What are the current staffing levels for RDM services in your institution? (FTE)

	Russell Group		Other 10%+		Other		Overall		Num. Responses
	Mean	Median	Mean	Median	Mean	Median	Mean	Median	
Library - fixed term staff	1.6	1.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.9	1.0	28
Library -permanent staff	0.9	0.4	0.9	1.0	0.8	1.0	0.9	1.0	33
Research Office - fixed term	0.1	0.0	0.4	0.0	2.7	0.0	0.7	0.0	17
Research Office - permanent	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.7	0.1	0.3	0.0	23
Computing/ IT Support - fixed term	1.3	1.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0	19
Computing/ IT Support - permanent	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.0	2.3	0.5	0.9	0.0	19
Schools, faculties or research groups - fixed term	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	8
Schools, faculties or research groups - permanent	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	8
TOTAL	4.7	3.1	2.6	1.0	6.4	1.6	4.4	2.0	

8. What staffing for RDM services do you expect there to be by May 2015? (FTE)

	Mean	Median	Mean	Median	Mean	Median	Mean	Median	Num. Responses
Library - fixed term staff	1.6	1.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.9	1.0	19
Library -permanent staff	1.6	1.0	1.2	1.2	0.9	1.0	1.3	1.0	34
Research Office - fixed term	2.0	2.0	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.3	10
Research Office - permanent	0.6	0.5	0.3	0.0	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.2	21
Computing/ IT Support - fixed term	2.4	1.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.3	12
Computing/ IT Support - permanent	1.4	1.0	0.6	0.0	0.6	0.5	0.8	0.5	17
Schools, faculties or research groups - fixed term	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4
Schools, faculties or research groups - permanent	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6
TOTAL	9.5	6.5	3.0	1.2	2.0	2.0	5.1	3.2	

